

Adversarial Fine-Tuning of Vision Models for Robustness to Sensitivity- and Invariance-Based Adversarial Examples

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Abstract—This thesis studies adversarial fine-tuning of MobileNetV3, ResNet50, and EfficientNet-B0 on Imagenette using sensitivity-based adversarial examples (SBAE) and invariance-based adversarial examples (IBAE). We compare SBAE-only, IBAE-only, and mixed training under a shared evaluation protocol with clean accuracy, Projected Gradient Descent (PGD) robustness, IBAE target-label accuracy, and invariance failure, and select checkpoints via a fixed composite score. Results from five-seed summaries show that baseline models maintain high clean accuracy but remain weakly robust, SBAE-only improves PGD robustness, IBAE-only best preserves clean performance while improving invariance robustness, and mixed training provides the best overall balance on higher-capacity backbones. ResNet50 mixed ranks highest under the selected policy, while MobileNetV3 shows stronger specialization effects. The study concludes that robust fine-tuning is architecture- and objective-dependent and should be guided by explicit deployment priorities.

Index Terms—Adversarial Machine Learning, Computer Vision, Robustness, Adversarial Training

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Motivation

Vision models increasingly act in safety-critical settings (e.g., perception for driving [1]). While clean-image accuracy has surged from classic digits recognition to transformer-based classifiers [2], small input changes can still flip predictions [3], and even physical tweaks can cause dangerous misreads (e.g., modified street signs) [4]. Such images are called sensitivity-based adversarial examples (SBAE). Beyond such sensitivity-based attacks, recent work shows models may also be overly invariant to semantically meaningful changes, producing invariance-based adversarial examples (IBAE) that fool humans and machines in opposite ways [5].

For intuition, consider two contrasting cases. In a sensitivity-based adversarial example, a visually almost unchanged image (e.g., a stop sign with small pixel-level perturbations) is misclassified by the model. In an invariance-based adversarial example, the image is changed in a semantically meaningful way toward another class for human observers, but the model prediction remains unchanged.

This work proposes to fine-tune pretrained Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) [6] on Imagenette with SBAE-

only, IBAE-only, and mixed adversarial training to study the robustness–accuracy trade-off.

The primary motivation of this work is to analyze how Machine Learning (ML) classifiers can be trained to be more robust against adversarial examples. So-called adversarial training incorporates adversarial examples in training which can lead to increased accuracy on malicious samples (which we call robustness), but might also negatively impact performance on benign examples (accuracy) [7]. Optimizing this robustness–accuracy trade-off and creating such a pipeline is a main goal of this work, which aims to answer the following research question: *How can sensitivity and invariance-based adversarial examples be used for fine-tuning deep learning image classifiers, to make them more robust against adversarial attacks?* Further, we aim to deepen our understanding of how the efficacy of robustness fine-tuning varies with classifier architecture and architecture regime.

To address this question, we combine scalable adversarial-example generation with adversarial fine-tuning across multiple architectures and evaluate the resulting robustness–accuracy trade-offs under clean and adversarial conditions.

B. Contributions

In this work we contribute the following to the field of adversarial Machine Learning:

- **Unified adversarial fine-tuning pipeline:** We implemented an end-to-end pipeline for SBAE-only, IBAE-only, and mixed robustness fine-tuning on Imagenette, including automated run logging and checkpoint selection.
- **Cross-architecture robustness study:** We performed a comparative evaluation across MobileNetV3, ResNet50, and EfficientNet-B0 under identical metric definitions and scoring protocol.
- **Robustness-aware model selection:** We introduced and applied a composite selection score and analyzed score decomposition to explain checkpoint ranking differences.
- **Empirical findings on robustness–accuracy trade-offs:** We show that mixed training gives the best overall scores on larger backbones (ResNet50, EfficientNet-B0), while

IBAE-only training is comparatively clean-preserving and can yield slight clean-accuracy gains.

C. Thesis Structure

This work is organized into seven chapters. Following this introduction and the statement of research questions, Chapter 2 reviews relevant background literature, Chapters 3 and 4 describe the methodology and implementation pipeline, Chapter 5 presents the experimental results, Chapter 6 discusses their implications and limitations, and Chapter 7 concludes with the main findings and directions for future work.

II. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

A. Machine Learning

For many years now, ML models have been embedded in applications that affect lives of millions, if not billions of people. Unlike rule-based pipelines with hand-crafted decision logic, ML systems learn decision boundaries from data; in this work we focus on image classifiers that map pixels to class labels. The theoretical foundations for Machine Learning have been laid more than 80 years ago. In 1943 McCulloch and Pitts [8] introduced the idea of modeling an algorithm after the brain using interconnected neurons. This idea was further developed in 1958, when Rosenblatt [9] introduced the idea of a perceptron. This approach computes a linear combination of all inputs to the neuron, adds a bias and feeds the output to a nonlinear activation function.

Putting multiple neurons next to each other gives us a so-called layer. We can stack multiple layers on top of each other and connect the neurons of each layer with the following one. We call such an arrangement a *multilayer perceptron* (MLP) [10].

For such a perceptron to be effective, the weights and biases of each neuron need to be specifically tuned. To accomplish this, we use a process called *back-propagation*, which was first applied to MLPs by Werbos in [11]. Back-propagation uses the chain rule of calculus to compute gradients of a loss function with respect to each weight and bias in the network. These gradients can then be used to update the weights and biases using an optimization algorithm like stochastic gradient descent (SGD), first introduced by Robbins and Monro in [12].

B. Computer Vision

One field where ML models are pervasive, is computer vision. These models are implemented e.g., in cars, where their usage ranges from recognizing street signs to fully autonomously driving the vehicle using optical sensor data. This data feeds into computer vision models, which then take decisions, like braking, accelerating, or turning. The performance of such models has seen dramatic increases. An important work in early ML for computer vision was presented by LeCun et al. in [6]. The authors proposed a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) architecture, which was able to classify handwritten digits with high accuracy. Since then, many more CNN architectures have been proposed, which further improved performance on image classification tasks.

A milestone in this development was ResNet [13], where the authors proposed residual connections, which made it possible to train very deep networks. More recently, transformer-based architectures have been proposed for computer vision tasks, which were originally developed for natural language processing tasks. An important work in this area is [2], where the authors proposed Vision Transformers (ViT), which achieved state-of-the-art performance on image classification tasks.

C. Adversarial Attacks

Since the work by Szegedy et al. in [3], we also know that it is possible to carefully modify images in a way which changes ML classifiers' predictions, while still looking almost identical to humans. Such images are called adversarial examples—specifically sensitivity-based adversarial examples (also called perturbation-based adversarial examples)—because malicious actors can use small perturbations to exploit the sensitivity of computer vision models and cause misclassifications.

Such misclassifications can be extremely dangerous. In [4], the authors were able to put stickers on stop signs, which led the ML classifier to misidentify the signs as speed limits of 45 mph.

Another class of adversarial examples is invariance-based adversarial examples (IBAE) which were first introduced by Jacobsen et al. in [5]. While sensitivity-based adversarial examples (SBAE) exploit the fact that models can be sensitive to small, even imperceptible perturbations, IBAE use the fact that machine classifiers can be overly invariant to changes in the input image, which makes it possible to make sizable and relevant changes to an image without affecting the final machine classification. Although the classifier maintains its predictions, most humans would now predict a different class. It was further shown by Tramer et al. in [14] that training for robustness against SBAE can actually make a model more susceptible to IBAE. The authors argue that the reason for this is a fundamental misalignment between human and machine perception.

The two classes of adversarial examples are illustrated in Figure 1, which illustrates the difference between sensitivity-based and invariance-based adversarial examples in feature space. Starting from a benign sample (black), a sensitivity-based perturbation (pink) introduces only a small change to the input but crosses the decision boundary, leading to misclassification. In contrast, an invariance-based perturbation (brown) induces a large, semantically meaningful change to the input while remaining on the same side of the decision boundary, such that the model prediction does not change. This highlights that models can be both overly sensitive to small perturbations and overly invariant to significant changes in the input.

D. Adversarial Training

In [15], the authors introduce a way to generate sensitivity-based adversarial examples which they call Fast Gradient Sign Method (FGSM). They use images generated in this way to augment the training data and show that this leads to increased

Fig. 1. Invariance-based (brown) and sensitivity-based (pink) image perturbations for a suboptimal decision boundary between two class distributions (blue and green). Sensitivity-based perturbations cross the boundary with little change, invariance-based ones exhibit large changes without crossing the boundary (Figure taken from [5]).

robustness against such adversarial examples. This approach is called adversarial training. These first approaches mainly targeted simple datasets like MNIST and CIFAR.

Kurakin et al. [16] first targeted more complex datasets by using adversarial training on ImageNet. The authors of [17] introduced Projected Gradient Descent (PGD) to generate SBAE, which they then use for adversarial training. This approach is still considered a strong baseline for adversarial training.

Performing adversarial training usually leads to a decrease in accuracy on benign images. This phenomenon is called the robustness–accuracy trade-off and was first studied in [7] and later formalized in [18].

More recently, Rauter et al. [19] investigated adversarial training in the presence of both sensitivity-based and invariance-based adversarial examples on the simplistic MNIST dataset. Their results show that robustness against these two attack types is inherently conflicting, and that simultaneous adversarial training can provide a practical trade-off, achieving balanced robustness against both.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Dataset and Task Definition

Aligning with work done in [20] and [21] we use Imagenette [22] as our main dataset, a subset of ImageNet [23]. ImageNet is a hierarchical image dataset which contains more than one million samples across 1000 classes. This dataset is widely used for training and evaluating image classification models. However, the large number of classes and the fine-grained nature of many of these classes can make it difficult to analyze model performance and robustness in a controlled way. Imagenette aims to provide a more manageable dataset for studying adversarial robustness, containing only ten easily distinguishable classes (tench, English springer, cassette player, chain saw, church, French horn, garbage truck, gas pump, golf ball, parachute). In total, Imagenette contains 13394 images, out of which 9469 are in the training set while 3925 are in the test set. This dataset provides easily understandable semantics, while still being diverse and large enough to be feasible for fine-tuning and adversarial training.

The primary task is 10-class image classification on Imagenette, with top-1 class prediction as the target output. In addition to standard clean-image classification performance, the thesis evaluates adversarial robustness under both sensitivity-based and invariance-based adversarial settings. Models are therefore optimized and compared not only by clean accuracy, but also by robustness-oriented metrics (Projected Gradient Descent (PGD) accuracy, IBAE target-label accuracy, and IBAE invariance failure rate). This establishes robustness-aware model selection as the central task.

B. Model Architectures

The aim of this work is to use different models and compare the results of adversarial training across each of them. The focus lies on Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) like MobileNetV3 [24], EfficientNet [25] or ResNet [13]. We build our models based on weights pretrained on ImageNet, which can be downloaded via PyTorch [26]. This means that the models have a final output layer with 1000 fully connected neurons, one for each output class. Since we do not want to classify 1000 classes, we need to adapt the models, such that they yield one out of ten output classes found in Imagenette. This is done by replacing the final classification layer with a newly initialized fully connected layer with 10 output neurons. We then freeze all weights in the neural network except for the last layer, and fine-tune on Imagenette data for five epochs. Not much training is needed to achieve almost perfect performance (>99% accuracy), since the bulk of the computation is done in all of the previous layers of the model. The convolutional layers learn features of the image which are then classified in the final feed forward layers. Finally we unfreeze the whole network and perform fine-tuning with a very low learning rate (10^{-5}). This is done to let the model learn small adaptations which might improve performance, since the goal of the model has slightly changed. This training procedure gives us our baseline models.

C. Adversarial Example Generation

For the generation of invariance-based Adversarial Examples we modified the algorithm from [21] to compute large volumes of IBAE. This approach creates IBAE by replacing the most important regions of an attack image with the most important regions of a base image. The importance of pixel data for the classification is extracted using methods from the field of Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) [27]. These XAI methods generate a heatmap signalling which pixels were important for the classifiers’ final decision and which were not. Based on this heatmap, a binary mask is computed and applied to the base image. The size of this mask is then iteratively increased until the classifier flips its prediction away from the label of the base image. Stepping back by one iteration yields the image with the maximum inserted attack content that is still classified with the base label. This algorithm is illustrated in Figure 2 and outlined in Algorithm 1, both taken from [21].

Fig. 2. Example invariance-based adversarial image used in this work (taken from [21]).

Algorithm 1: Generating IBAE using patch-insertion (taken from [21]).

Input: images X , labels Y , model M , explainability algorithm XAI

Result: List of IBAE-candidates X_{ibae}

```

1  $X, Y \leftarrow \text{sort\_pairs}(X, Y)$ 
2  $\text{importance\_maps} \leftarrow XAI.\text{attribute}(X, Y, M)$ 
3  $I_{\text{base}}, I_{\text{atk}} \leftarrow \text{array\_split}(\text{importance\_maps}, 2)$ 
4  $X_{\text{base}}, X_{\text{atk}} \leftarrow \text{array\_split}(X, 2)$ 
5  $Y_{\text{base}}, Y_{\text{atk}} \leftarrow \text{array\_split}(Y, 2)$ 
6 for  $x_{\text{base}}, x_{\text{atk}}, i_{\text{base}}, i_{\text{atk}}, y_{\text{base}}$  in  $\{X_{\text{base}}, X_{\text{atk}}, I_{\text{base}}, I_{\text{atk}}, Y_{\text{base}}\}$  do
7    $\alpha \leftarrow 0.01$ 
8   while true do
9      $a_{\{\text{base}, \text{atk}\}} \leftarrow \alpha\text{-quantile of all } i_{\{\text{base}, \text{atk}\}}\text{-values}$ 
10     $\text{mask}_{\{\text{base}, \text{atk}\}} \leftarrow 1$  where  $i_{\{\text{base}, \text{atk}\}} > a_{\{\text{base}, \text{atk}\}}$  else 0
11     $\text{offset} \leftarrow \text{center\_of\_mass}(\text{mask}_{\text{base}}) -$ 
12       $\text{center\_of\_mass}(\text{mask}_{\text{atk}})$ 
13     $x_{\text{atk}} \leftarrow \text{translate}(x_{\text{atk}}, \text{offset})$ 
14     $\text{ibae\_candidate} \leftarrow x_{\text{atk}}$  where  $\text{mask}_{\text{base}} = 1$  else  $x_{\text{base}}$ 
15    if  $M.\text{predict}(\text{ibae\_candidate}) = y_{\text{base}}$  then
16       $\alpha \leftarrow \alpha + 0.01$ 
17       $\text{last\_img} \leftarrow \text{ibae\_candidate}$ 
18    else
19       $X_{\text{ibae}}.\text{append}(\text{last\_img})$ 
20       $\alpha \leftarrow \alpha - 0.01$ 
21      break
22    end
23  end

```

The algorithm as published in [21] uses each image in the validation set of Imagenette only once, combining each image pairwise. To increase the number of available images, we first used the training set, instead of the validation set, giving us 9469 images to work with. Additionally, we now construct

image pairs by randomly sampling two images with different labels, while enforcing uniqueness of each pair. If a sampled pair has already been used, a new pair is drawn. To determine how many pairs we can construct in this way, we can make the following estimation:

Let n denote the total number of images and n_i the number of images belonging to class $i \in \{1, \dots, 10\}$. The total number of unordered image pairs is given by $\binom{n}{2}$. Since we only consider pairs of images with different labels, we subtract all same-class pairs, yielding

$$N_{\text{pairs}} = \binom{n}{2} - \sum_{i=1}^{10} \binom{n_i}{2}.$$

We assume an approximately balanced dataset, where $n_i \approx \frac{n}{10}$, so this simplifies to

$$N_{\text{pairs}} \approx \frac{9}{10} \binom{n}{2},$$

$\binom{n}{2}$ is on the order of n^2 , showing that the number of valid image pairs grows quadratically with the dataset size. For $n = 9469$ this equals 4.034×10^7 . Given that the number of possible image pairs is on the order of tens of millions, this results in a practically inexhaustible pool of potential IBAE. This is important because it enables scalable data generation for adversarial fine-tuning while maintaining pair diversity.

For the generation of sensitivity-based adversarial examples, we use the PGD attack [17]. This attack is an iterative version of the Fast Gradient Sign Method (FGSM) [15], which was one of the first methods to generate adversarial examples. PGD iteratively applies FGSM with a small step size and

projects the perturbed image back onto the ϵ -ball around the original image to ensure that the perturbation remains within a specified limit. Here, ϵ is the perturbation budget (typically an L_∞ bound) that limits the maximum per-pixel change from the original image, controlling attack strength. This allows us to generate strong adversarial examples that can effectively test and improve the robustness of our models during training. We apply the PGD attack dynamically during training, which means that for each batch of images, we generate new adversarial examples on-the-fly, rather than pre-generating them. This approach allows us to create a more diverse set of adversarial examples and can lead to better robustness during training.

D. Training Regimes

In this work, a training regime refers to the specific composition of training data used during adversarial fine-tuning (e.g., SBAE-only, IBAE-only, or mixed clean/SBAE/IBAE training). Robustness training is implemented as adversarial finetuning: we continue training our baseline models on attack images so the parameters adapt to those perturbations. This process works similarly to the original training procedure, used when creating the models. We feed in images, let the model predict the output, calculate the loss (i.e., how wrong the model was), and modify the weights of the models by using backpropagation and gradient descent [28]. The only difference is the input data that we feed into the model. While in the original training clean images are used, here we use our crafted Adversarial Examples to train our models to be more robust against such attacks. To analyze the interaction of different types of robustness, we first fine-tune only on SBAE, generated via PGD [17]. We then reset to the baseline model and train it on IBAE only. Finally we trained the baseline model on a mixture of clean images, SBAE and IBAE, evaluating different mixtures. For mixed training, the loss components are combined with explicit weights (w_{clean} , w_{SBAE} , w_{IBAE}).

In data-volume terms, each architecture used a pre-generated IBAE pool with a target size of up to 10 000 images (as described in Section IV-E). Clean-data fine-tuning was performed on the Imagenette training split (9469 images) for 8 epochs with batch size 16. SBAE were generated on-the-fly from clean batches via PGD during training, while IBAE were loaded from the corresponding architecture-specific pre-generated pool and incorporated according to the selected regime weights.

a) Regime-weight selection rationale.: The loss weights were chosen using a practical combination of planned objectives and early experimental results. We use SBAE-only with $(w_{\text{clean}}, w_{\text{SBAE}}, w_{\text{IBAE}}) = (0.2, 0.8, 0.0)$ and IBAE-only with $(0.5, 0.0, 0.5)$ to focus on the target robustness objective while still keeping clean accuracy stable. For mixed training, we chose $(0.25, 0.25, 0.5)$ after exploratory ablations indicated that IBAE-leaning mixtures produced stronger aggregate behavior than more SBAE-heavy alternatives in our setting. In particular, candidate mixtures with lower IBAE weight

(e.g., $(0.2, 0.6, 0.2)$ and $(0.25, 0.35, 0.4)$) underperformed compared with IBAE-leaning variants (e.g., $(0.2, 0.3, 0.5)$ and $(0.25, 0.25, 0.5)$), with $(0.25, 0.25, 0.5)$ yielding the best mixed-run score among those tested in the early experiments. We therefore interpret the final mixed weighting as a pragmatic compromise which preserves clean behavior, retains good SBAE robustness, and allocates additional capacity to invariance robustness, which was empirically harder to stabilize under mixed optimization.

E. Evaluation Metrics and Composite Score

To compare checkpoints across regimes and select the best model within each run, we use four evaluation metrics: clean accuracy, PGD robustness, IBAE target-label accuracy, and IBAE invariance failure rate. In addition, we define a composite score for checkpoint comparison across regimes. This composite score is defined as $S(m) = 0.4 A_{\text{clean}}(m) + 0.3 A_{\text{PGD}}(m) + 0.3 A_{\text{IBAE}}(m)$, where A_{clean} , A_{PGD} , and A_{IBAE} are the respective accuracies for model m . The score weights were selected as a practical policy choice rather than by formal optimization. We assign the largest weight to clean accuracy (0.4) to ensure that benign-image performance remains a primary constraint, while the remaining weight is split equally between PGD robustness (0.3) and IBAE robustness (0.3) so that both adversarial perspectives contribute comparably to model ranking. This weighting reflects the objective of the thesis: prioritize models that maintain high clean performance while achieving balanced robustness across sensitivity-based and invariance-based attacks.

F. Experimental Protocol and Reproducibility

All experiments follow a fixed protocol to ensure comparability across architectures and training regimes. Starting from ImageNet-pretrained backbones adapted to 10 output classes, we evaluate baseline fine-tuning, SBAE-only, IBAE-only, and mixed adversarial training under a shared data split and a common set of evaluation metrics. For each run, checkpoint selection is based on the same robustness-aware composite score, while clean and adversarial metrics are reported separately to illustrate robustness–accuracy trade-offs.

To improve reproducibility, experiments are executed through a configuration-driven pipeline with explicit run tags, saved checkpoints, and structured result artifacts (CSV/JSON) in dedicated output directories. Random seeds are fixed where applicable, and all key hyperparameters (learning rate, epoch count, adversarial threat settings, and regime weights) are stored with run outputs. This enables deterministic reconstruction of reported tables and plots from logged experiment files. For IBAE artifacts specifically, we also added a save–reload validation step to verify that on-disk images are numerically consistent with in-memory images before they are used in robustness training and evaluation.

G. Seed Aggregation Protocol

The seeded robustness summary is computed from five runs with seeds {42, 1337, 2026, 7, 31415}. For each seed and each

architecture–regime pair, the selected entry is the run-internal best checkpoint under the fixed score rule ($0.4 A_{\text{clean}}(m) + 0.3 A_{\text{PGD}}(m) + 0.3 A_{\text{IBAE}}(m)$). Seed-level results are then aggregated by mean, standard deviation, minimum, and maximum. For uncertainty reporting, we compute 95% confidence intervals using a t-based critical value with run-count-dependent degrees of freedom: $t_{0.975, n-1} \cdot s / \sqrt{n}$. This protocol keeps checkpoint selection consistent within each run while making cross-seed uncertainty explicit at reporting time.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

A. Codebase Overview

Most of the code was implemented using Jupyter Notebooks. Additional Python files, containing utility functions, were used to keep the notebooks concise. The main steps in the pipeline were the finetuning of the ImageNet-pretrained models to 10 output classes, the pipeline for the creation of adversarial examples and finally the adversarial fine-tuning and evaluation of results.

B. Model Fine-Tuning Pipeline

For our experiments we evaluated MobileNetV3, EfficientNet as well as ResNet50. We first loaded the pretrained weights directly from PyTorch. Since these models were trained to classify images from ImageNet, the final output layer had 1000 neurons. We replaced this layer with a ten neuron fully connected layer. These neurons had randomly initialized weights, and as such were not able to consistently classify images. Next, we froze all weights except the ones in the final layer, i.e. we told PyTorch to not update the weights of all layers except the final one when training. We then fed Imagenette samples into the model, and fine-tuned it. This was done for five epochs, using cross-entropy loss and AdamW [29] with a learning rate of 10^{-3} as optimizer. AdamW is a very common optimizer, which adds weight decay to the original Adam optimizer, a common regularization technique. This allowed us to achieve almost perfect performance on the clean data (>99% accuracy) with only training the final layer, since the convolutional layers had already learned useful features during pretraining on ImageNet. Additionally, after the final layer had been trained, we unfroze all weights and continued fine-tuning the model for five additional epochs with a much lower learning rate of 10^{-5} . This was done to let the model learn small adaptations in the convolutional layers, which might further improve performance, since the goal of the model had slightly changed. After that, the baseline model was evaluated on Imagenette data and then saved to disk for further experimentation.

C. IBAE/SBAE Data Pipelines

The pipeline for the generation of our IBAE had multiple inputs. First, it needed images from which to generate the IBAE, here the Imagenette training set was used. Second, we chose an XAI method to measure pixel importance. For our experiments we chose XGradCam, a variation of Grad-CAM [30], which was shown to be well suited for the

generation of IBAE [21]. These XAI methods needed an image classification model as input, here we used our Imagenette fine-tuned baseline models. We pre-generated IBAE for each image classification model, these images were saved to disk, and were later loaded by a custom PyTorch Dataloader, to be used for the robustness fine-tuning.

During early experiments we observed a consistency issue between in-memory and on-disk IBAE artifacts. By construction, generated IBAE should preserve the source-model decision constraint during creation, which implies a 0% target-label accuracy check for the baseline model when evaluated on these artifacts. This property held for images kept in memory, but not always for images that were saved and reloaded from disk. We therefore tested the serialization path explicitly by saving generated IBAE, reloading them, and performing a pixel-wise comparison against the in-memory tensors.

The root cause was in the export pipeline. The original implementation saved images as JPEG, which introduces lossy compression and therefore modifies pixel values. Switching to PNG reduced the discrepancy, but did not fully eliminate it in the previous conversion path because images were written from NumPy arrays in an 8-bit unsigned integer representation. After standardizing the save path with explicit float32 handling before export and using a lossless output format (TIFF in the final pipeline), after saving and reloading, the images were pixel-wise identical to the in-memory version. With this correction in place, the expected 0% target-label accuracy check was restored for the corresponding baseline verification step.

For our SBAE robustness training, we did not pre-generate our images; instead the PGD attack was performed dynamically during training. For PGD, we needed to define some hyperparameters for the attack. During training we used $\epsilon = 2/255$, where ϵ is a measure for the strength of the attack. Recall that SBAE attacks introduce carefully crafted pixel modification, which to the human eye seem like random noise. The higher ϵ is, the stronger the pixel can be manipulated by PGD. This attack is also performed iteratively, which means we run multiple (in our case three) iterations of this attack. These hyperparameters are often denoted as *PGD3@2/255*.

D. Experiment Runner and Result Aggregation

Once the baseline models as well as the necessary IBAE were in place, the actual adversarial fine-tuning could take place. For each of the three classifiers, we first ran evaluations on the baseline model. We then performed SBAE-only fine-tuning, followed by IBAE-only. Finally we performed mixed training, using different weights for each of the three categories (clean, SBAE, IBAE). During fine-tuning, the loss of the model was calculated with respect to each metric and then weighted accordingly. This way, the fine-tuning targeted different accuracies.

In implementation terms, the experiment runner executed architecture–regime combinations sequentially, evaluated checkpoints after each epoch, and persisted both best-model checkpoints and full metric histories. This design en-

abled fault-tolerant continuation and traceable post-hoc analysis: each final CSV row contained regime configuration (weights, PGD settings, epoch count, learning rate), scores, and completion timestamps. In practice, this logging strategy made it straightforward to reconstruct runtime behavior and compare computational cost across architectures without introducing additional profiling tooling.

During fine-tuning, checkpoint selection and overall run ranking were based on the aggregate score defined in Section III-E.

E. Execution Environment and Compute Budget

All experiments were executed locally on a Mac Studio with Apple M2 Ultra and 64 GB RAM, using a Conda-managed Python 3.12 environment and PyTorch on the MPS backend. The main adversarial fine-tuning configuration used image size 320, batch size 16, eight adversarial fine-tuning epochs, and learning rate 10^{-5} . For IBAE generation, we used XGradCAM with cutoff 0.5 (meaning we only accept IBAE where the majority of pixels came from the attack image), pair-batch size 32, and target 10 000 generated IBAE per architecture.

Empirical wall-clock runtime was logged from pipeline outputs and timestamped log files. IBAE generation for 10 000 samples required approximately 1h18m (MobileNet), 1h31m (ResNet), and 1h47m (EfficientNet). This corresponds to an average generation rate of approximately two IBAE per second. For adversarial fine-tuning runs (eight epochs per regime), observed per-regime runtimes were approximately 52m for MobileNet, 1h24m for ResNet, and 1h38m minutes for EfficientNet. These values are reported as practical runtime estimates on the stated hardware/software stack and are intended to support reproducibility planning rather than strict hardware-independent benchmarks.

For baseline adaptation from ImageNet-pretrained models to 10-class Imagenette classifiers, wall-clock times were also recorded in two stages. For MobileNetV3, training only the final classification layer required about five minutes, followed by about seven additional minutes for full-network fine-tuning. For ResNet50, the corresponding times were about seven minutes (final layer) and 11 minutes (full-network fine-tuning). For EfficientNet-B0, the times were about six minutes and 10 minutes, respectively. In total, baseline preparation therefore required roughly 12 minutes for MobileNetV3, 18 minutes for ResNet50, and 16 minutes for EfficientNet-B0 on the stated hardware. Reported runtimes include per-epoch evaluation for performance tracking; a production-focused pipeline could reduce wall-clock time by evaluating less frequently.

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

A. Per-Architecture Regime Comparisons

For each architecture (MobileNetV3, ResNet50, and EfficientNet-B0), we compared baseline, SBAE-only, IBAE-only, and mixed training under an identical evaluation protocol. Unless stated otherwise, adversarial-regime entries reflected the automatically tracked best checkpoint over the 8-epoch fine-tuning run. Across all models, baseline checkpoints

retained strong clean accuracy but showed weak robustness on adversarial metrics. SBAE-only training typically (and unsurprisingly) improved PGD robustness, while IBAE-only training improved semantic robustness on IBAE data and reduced invariance-related failure behavior. Mixed training provided the most balanced trade-off in the stronger backbones, indicating that joint optimization over clean, SBAE, and IBAE objectives was beneficial when model capacity was sufficient. Unless stated otherwise, all reported scores and accuracies are means over five runs with different random seeds, with standard deviations and confidence intervals computed using a t-based critical value for 95% confidence.

Fig. 3. Best aggregate score per training regime within each architecture (five-seed mean \pm 95% confidence interval).

Table I compares baseline (the model after standard clean fine-tuning, without adversarial fine-tuning), SBAE-only, IBAE-only, and mixed training within each architecture. Table I summarizes the regime-wise best checkpoints within each architecture. A shared baseline pattern appeared across all three models: clean performance was consistently high ($> 99\%$), but robustness was weak without adversarial fine-tuning. In particular, all baseline checkpoints had IBAE target-label accuracy of 0, which is expected because IBAE are constructed to preserve the model’s original prediction. This baseline behavior is important for interpreting the gains from each training regime: nearly all score improvements came from robustness terms, not from changes in clean accuracy.

For **MobileNetV3**, the strongest regime was IBAE-only training (mean score 0.7018), followed by SBAE-only (0.6788) and mixed (0.6613). The metric profile revealed a pronounced specialization effect: IBAE-only achieved high IBAE target-label accuracy (0.8461) and low invariance failure (0.1300), but relatively modest PGD accuracy (0.1653). SBAE-only exhibited the opposite tendency, with much stronger PGD robustness (0.5229) but lower IBAE target-label accuracy (0.4329). Mixed training did improve over baseline, but it did not dominate either specialized regime on its primary strength, suggesting that this smaller backbone could not simultaneously optimize both robustness dimensions as effectively as the larger models. In other words, MobileNet appeared more sensitive to objective competition between perturbation robustness and invariance robustness.

For **ResNet50**, all adversarial regimes produced large gains over baseline (mean score 0.4387), but mixed training clearly

TABLE I
PER-ARCHITECTURE REGIME COMPARISON (BEST CHECKPOINT PER REGIME). HIGHER IS BETTER FOR CLEAN/PGD/IBAE/SCORE; LOWER IS BETTER FOR INVARIANCE FAILURE. BOLD VALUES INDICATE THE BEST REGIME WITHIN EACH ARCHITECTURE BLOCK.

Architecture	Regime	Clean Acc	PGD Acc	IBAE Acc	IBAE Invariance	Score
MobileNetV3	Baseline	0.9929	0.0294	0.0000	1.0000	0.4060
	SBAE-only	0.9802	0.5229	0.4329	0.4756	0.6788
	IBAE-only	0.9960	0.1653	0.8461	0.1300	0.7018
	Mixed	0.9885	0.2818	0.6045	0.3411	0.6613
ResNet50	Baseline	0.9952	0.1355	0.0000	1.0000	0.4387
	SBAE-only	0.9921	0.6869	0.7345	0.2047	0.8233
	IBAE-only	0.9977	0.5091	0.9701	0.0230	0.8428
	Mixed	0.9978	0.6085	0.9431	0.0446	0.8646
EfficientNet-B0	Baseline	0.9918	0.1391	0.0000	1.0000	0.4385
	SBAE-only	0.9897	0.5999	0.5639	0.3634	0.7450
	IBAE-only	0.9945	0.3356	0.8560	0.1173	0.7553
	Mixed	0.9934	0.4652	0.8431	0.1241	0.7899

led (mean score 0.8646). Notably, ResNet mixed was not only strong in aggregate score but remained strong in each component: clean accuracy stayed high (0.9978), PGD accuracy was high (0.6085), and IBAE target-label accuracy was also high (0.9431), with low invariance failure (0.0446). This balanced profile explains why mixed training ranked above the specialized variants despite IBAE-only reaching the best IBAE term (0.9701) and SBAE-only reaching the best PGD term (0.6869). The evidence indicated that ResNet had sufficient capacity to preserve clean performance while absorbing both robustness objectives in a single regime, making it less dependent on specialization than MobileNet.

For **EfficientNet-B0**, the pattern sat between MobileNet and ResNet. Mixed training was best overall (mean score 0.7899), with absolute gains of 0.0346 over IBAE-only (0.7553) and 0.0448 over SBAE-only (0.7450). Relative to ResNet, this lead was larger than the mixed-vs-IBAE gap ($0.8646 - 0.8428 = 0.0217$) and similar to the mixed-vs-SBAE gap ($0.8646 - 0.8233 = 0.0413$), so EfficientNet still showed a meaningful mixed-regime advantage. EfficientNet mixed combined strong IBAE target-label accuracy (0.8431) with moderate PGD accuracy (0.4652) and low invariance failure (0.1241), yielding the most balanced trade-off for this architecture. At the same time, the specialized regimes still showed expected strengths: SBAE-only had stronger PGD performance (0.5999) than mixed, while IBAE-only slightly improved clean accuracy and supported stronger invariance-focused behavior. This suggested that EfficientNet benefited from joint optimization, but still retained visible regime-specific preferences.

Taken together, Table I and the architecture-wise discussion shows a consistent architecture–regime interaction: baseline checkpoints were robustly weak across adversarial metrics; specialized regimes recovered one robustness axis strongly; and mixed training gave the best within-architecture balance in higher-capacity backbones. This motivates the global cross-architecture comparison in the next section.

B. Cross-Architecture Comparison

Comparing best-performing checkpoints per architecture revealed a clear ranking structure that was not explained

by regime choice alone. Even though all architectures were trained and evaluated under the same protocol, ResNet50 achieved the strongest balance between robustness and accuracy, EfficientNet-B0 formed a second tier, and MobileNetV3 trailed on the aggregate score. This ordering indicated that architecture capacity and representational flexibility played a central role in how effectively mixed robustness objectives could be absorbed during fine-tuning.

As shown in Table I, the top architecture-level checkpoint was ResNet50 mixed (mean score 0.8646), followed by EfficientNet mixed (0.7899) and MobileNet IBAE-only (0.7018). The absolute gaps were non-trivial: ResNet led EfficientNet by about 0.0747 score points and led MobileNet by about 0.1627. These margins were large relative to the smaller regime-level differences observed within architectures, which suggested that architecture selection was one of the most important design choices in this setting.

Table II sharpens this picture by decomposing the total score into clean, PGD, and IBAE contributions. First, clean contributions are tightly clustered (roughly 0.397 to 0.399), so ranking is not primarily driven by clean accuracy. Second, the relative ordering is dominated by robustness balance: ResNet mixed combines a strong PGD term (0.1825) with a strong IBAE term (0.2829), yielding the best total score. By contrast, ResNet IBAE-only raises the IBAE contribution further (0.2910) but gives up PGD contribution (0.1527), while ResNet SBAE-only does the opposite with higher PGD contribution (0.2061) but lower IBAE contribution (0.2204). This confirms that the top rank emerges from balance rather than maximization of a single robustness axis.

The table also clarifies the cross-architecture hierarchy among non-ResNet models. EfficientNet mixed and EfficientNet IBAE-only remained competitive in clean and IBAE terms, but both had weaker PGD contribution than the top ResNet variants, which limited their total score. In practical terms, this meant EfficientNet could also become quite robust but did not fully close the gap to ResNet under the current objective weighting. MobileNet did not appear in the top-5 decomposition despite a strong IBAE-only checkpoint in its own architecture, indicating that architecture-level constraints remained visible even when regime tuning was effective.

TABLE II

SCORE DECOMPOSITION FOR THE TOP-5 CHECKPOINTS. THE FINAL SCORE IS COMPUTED AS $0.4 A_{\text{clean}}(m) + 0.3 A_{\text{PGD}}(m) + 0.3 A_{\text{IBAE}}(m)$.

Checkpoint	0.4-Clean	0.3-PGD	0.3-IBAE	Total Score
ResNet mixed	0.3991	0.1825	0.2829	0.8646
ResNet IBAE-only	0.3991	0.1527	0.2910	0.8428
ResNet SBAE-only	0.3968	0.2061	0.2204	0.8233
EfficientNet mixed	0.3974	0.1396	0.2529	0.7899
EfficientNet IBAE-only	0.3978	0.1007	0.2568	0.7553

An important implication for model selection was that the chosen score weights encode deployment priorities, and therefore influence which checkpoint is optimal. Under the present weighting (0.4/0.3/0.3), balanced models are favored. If a deployment heavily prioritizes one threat type, a specialized checkpoint could become preferable. However, given the current objective and the observed decomposition, the ranking was internally coherent: ResNet mixed was selected because it achieved strong clean performance while maintaining simultaneously high perturbation robustness and invariance robustness.

C. Impact of Adversarial Fine-Tuning on Clean-Accuracy

This subsection characterizes how adversarial fine-tuning affected benign-image performance. Figure 4 isolates regime-induced change relative to each architecture baseline.

Across architectures, IBAE-only fine-tuning was the most clean-preserving regime. Relative to baseline (5-seed means), each model showed a small positive delta: MobileNetV3 gained +0.0032, ResNet50 +0.0025, and EfficientNet-B0 +0.0026. In contrast, SBAE-only led to clean-accuracy drops across all architectures, with MobileNetV3 dropping by -0.0126 , ResNet50 by -0.0031 , and EfficientNet-B0 by -0.0021 . Mixed training showed a drop for MobileNetV3 of -0.0044 , but slight increases for ResNet50 (+0.0026) and EfficientNet-B0 (+0.0016). The practical pattern was therefore not a uniform robustness–accuracy trade-off, but a regime- and architecture-dependent trade-off where IBAE-focused updates tended to preserve or even slightly improve clean accuracy. Possible mechanisms behind this pattern are discussed in Section VI.

Across all settings, clean accuracy remained high, but the effect of adversarial fine-tuning depended on both regime and architecture.

As shown in Figure 4, IBAE-only training was near-neutral or slightly positive on clean accuracy, while SBAE-only and mixed regimes more often incurred a small clean-performance penalty.

Two caveats are important for interpreting these clean-accuracy effects. First, the presented values use five-seed summaries, but confidence intervals should still be treated as moderate-sample estimates rather than asymptotic bounds. Second, clean behavior and robustness ranking are connected to the current objective definition (including score weights and threat settings such as PGD evaluation strength and the specific IBAE generation process). Different weighting choices or stronger attack settings could shift the preferred trade-off.

Fig. 4. Change in clean validation accuracy relative to each architecture’s baseline model (five-seed mean \pm 95% confidence interval). Positive values indicate clean-accuracy gains over baseline, negative values indicate losses.

Nevertheless, within the present protocol, the main conclusion is stable: clean degradation is not an unavoidable consequence of adversarial fine-tuning, and its magnitude strongly depends on how robustness objectives are defined.

D. Best Checkpoint Selection

To ensure consistent ranking across runs and regimes, checkpoint quality is evaluated with the aggregate score ($0.4 A_{\text{clean}}(m) + 0.3 A_{\text{PGD}}(m) + 0.3 A_{\text{IBAE}}(m)$). During training, the pipeline evaluates checkpoints epoch-by-epoch and keeps the current best model whenever this score improves over the previously best checkpoint. For adversarial regimes, this process is applied over the configured eight fine-tuning epochs; baseline entries correspond to the no-adversarial-fine-tuning case.

Under this rule, the mixed ResNet configuration achieved the highest overall score, followed by ResNet IBAE-only and ResNet SBAE-only. This ordering was consistent with the decomposition in Table II: the winning checkpoint was not necessarily the strongest on a single robustness axis, but the one that sustained strong performance across both PGD and IBAE terms while preserving clean accuracy. In the five-seed analysis, the same winner remained top-1 in all seeds (5/5), which strengthened the stability of this ranking under run-to-run variation. In other words, the ranking depended on the chosen score definition and should not be interpreted as an absolute property of the architecture.

Figure 5 summarizes the seed-aggregated uncertainty. The ordering of top checkpoints is unchanged relative to the single-run analysis, and confidence intervals for the leading checkpoints remain separated from lower-tier models, supporting

Fig. 5. Mean score with 95% confidence intervals (t-based) across five seeds for each architecture/regime checkpoint.

the robustness of the main ranking claims under this five-seed setup.

If deployment priorities emphasize one threat type more strongly than the current weighting, a specialized checkpoint (e.g., SBAE-only or IBAE-only) could become preferable. However, for the stated objective in this work, the automatically tracked best checkpoint is internally coherent with the intended balance between benign performance and adversarial robustness. Figure 6 provides the global checkpoint ranking induced by this score-based tracking rule.

E. Training Dynamics and Weight-Sensitivity Analysis

To complement best-checkpoint summaries, we analyzed epoch-wise training histories for each architecture/regime and a small score-weight sensitivity study. The history analysis uses the logged per-epoch metrics (clean, PGD, IBAE, aggregate score), while the sensitivity analysis re-ranks checkpoints under alternative score weights. Together, these analyses clarify both *how* robustness is learned over time and *how stable* final model rankings are under moderate policy changes.

In Figure 7, the top row shows that score gains are strongest in early-to-mid epochs, with later epochs mostly refining trade-offs between PGD and IBAE terms. For ResNet50, mixed training continues improving through epoch 8 and reaches the best final score (0.8597), while IBAE-only peaks earlier and then plateaus in aggregate score despite continued IBAE gains. For EfficientNet-B0, mixed and SBAE-only rise steadily to late epochs, whereas IBAE-only peaks earlier and then declines mildly as PGD robustness decreases. MobileNetV3 exhibits stable learning in all adversarial regimes; IBAE-only and SBAE-only improve nearly monotonically, while mixed peaks near the end with a small final-epoch dip.

In the lower rows of Figure 7, the metric-level trajectories reinforce this interpretation: larger backbones (ResNet50 and EfficientNet-B0) sustain mixed-objective improvements later into training, while specialized IBAE-only runs can saturate earlier in aggregate score due to PGD drift even when IBAE target-label accuracy still increases. This dynamic supports the use of epoch-wise checkpoint tracking rather than relying only on final-epoch models.

For score-weight sensitivity, we compared the default weighting (0.4/0.3/0.3 for clean/PGD/IBAE) with two alter-

natives: clean-priority (0.5/0.25/0.25) and robustness-priority (0.3/0.35/0.35).

The top-5 ordering remained unchanged across all tested policies (ResNet50 mixed, ResNet50 IBAE-only, ResNet50 SBAE-only, EfficientNet-B0 mixed, EfficientNet-B0 IBAE-only), indicating that the main ranking conclusions were robust to moderate score reweighting in this range.

Figure 8 additionally shows that while absolute policy scores shift with weighting, the winning checkpoint identity remains stable (ResNet mixed). This supports the conclusion that model selection is robust under moderate policy reweighting in the tested range.

F. Cross-Source IBAE Transfer in ResNet Mixed Training

To test whether mixed-training gains transfer across IBAE source models, we ran an additional focused experiment for ResNet50 mixed training using the same optimization setup ($w_{\text{clean}} = 0.25$, $w_{\text{SBAE}} = 0.25$, $w_{\text{IBAE}} = 0.5$), which was used for mixed training, but replacing the IBAE training source. We compared the original in-domain ResNet mixed run (trained with ResNet-generated IBAE) against two cross-source variants trained on EfficientNet-generated and MobileNet-generated IBAE.

Figure 9 complements Table III. The aggregate score declines under both cross-source settings, while clean accuracy remains effectively unchanged. The right panel isolates this effect on the invariance axis: IBAE target-label accuracy is highest for in-domain source training and lower for both cross-source variants. This supports the interpretation that IBAE supervision is not fully source-agnostic in the current setup.

Table III shows that clean accuracy was effectively unchanged across all three variants, while robustness metrics degraded in both cross-source settings. Relative to in-domain ResNet-source mixed training, EfficientNet-source training reduced aggregate score by about 0.0229, and MobileNet-source training reduced it by about 0.0277. The drop was driven by lower PGD robustness and lower IBAE target-label accuracy, alongside higher invariance failure rates. Between the two cross-source runs, EfficientNet-source transfer was slightly stronger than MobileNet-source transfer (score difference ≈ 0.0048), but both remained below the in-domain reference.

These results provide directional evidence that IBAE-driven mixed training is not fully source-agnostic: the model used to generate IBAE appeared to affect how well robustness transferred. Because this comparison is based on a single run per source, the effect should be interpreted as a robust trend candidate rather than a definitive statistical claim.

VI. DISCUSSION

A. Robustness–Accuracy Trade-offs

The results show that the robustness–accuracy trade-off is not a single fixed curve, but a consequence of *which robustness objective is optimized*. As shown in the previous chapter, SBAE-only, IBAE-only, and mixed training each move the model in different directions. SBAE-only primarily hardens

Fig. 6. Top-ranked checkpoints by aggregate score (five-seed mean \pm 95% confidence interval). This ranking is used for final model selection.

TABLE III
RESNET MIXED TRAINING UNDER DIFFERENT IBAE SOURCE MODELS. HIGHER IS BETTER FOR CLEAN/PGD/IBAE/SCORE; LOWER IS BETTER FOR INVARIANCE FAILURE. BOLD VALUES INDICATE THE BEST SOURCE SETTING PER METRIC.

IBAE source	Clean Acc	PGD Acc	IBAE Acc	IBAE Invariance	Score
ResNet (in-domain)	0.9977	0.5997	0.9355	0.0500	0.8597
EfficientNet (cross-source)	0.9977	0.5753	0.8835	0.1050	0.8367
MobileNet (cross-source)	0.9977	0.5748	0.8680	0.1190	0.8319

local decision boundaries against perturbations (stronger PGD behavior), while IBAE-only primarily improves invariance-related behavior. Mixed training acts as a multi-objective compromise, but the quality of that compromise depends on model capacity.

This helps explain why clean-accuracy effects are generally small but not identical across regimes. IBAE-focused updates appear less disruptive to benign decision structure, which is consistent with their tendency to preserve (or slightly improve) clean performance. One possible explanation for this is that IBAE act as a form of data augmentation that encourages semantically meaningful feature learning without strongly distorting the input space. Mixed training combines both objectives, so its clean-accuracy effect depends on how these objectives interact during optimization and how they compete for representational capacity in the model. In contrast, stronger perturbation-oriented training can introduce mild clean-accuracy costs, especially in lower-capacity settings where representational budget is limited. In short, the trade-off depends on the training objective and model capacity, and is not an unavoidable effect of adversarial training.

For practical model selection, threat priorities should be defined first, and regime choice second. If perturbation robustness is the main objective, SBAE-only or mixed regimes can be justified even with a small clean-accuracy penalty. If clean performance must be preserved, or invariance-based attacks

are expected, IBAE-only or mixed training may be preferable. In short, the optimal regime is deployment-dependent rather than universal. Because these conclusions are supported by five-seed summaries with confidence intervals, they should be treated as robust within the present setup while still remaining conditional on dataset and threat-model scope. From a deployment perspective, IBAE-only is often the safer default when clean accuracy must be preserved. If perturbation robustness is the primary requirement, a modest clean-accuracy penalty under SBAE-only or mixed regimes can be acceptable, especially in higher-capacity architectures such as ResNet50. This motivates the architecture-specific interpretation in the next section.

B. Architecture-Specific Effects

Beyond regime-level averages, the experiments show that architecture changes how robustness objectives interact during fine-tuning. Since all models were trained and evaluated under the same protocol, the differences are best read as architecture- and capacity-related effects.

Across architectures, performance follows a clear capacity-related pattern. MobileNetV3 behaves more like a specialization model: it benefits when one robustness objective is emphasized, but mixed optimization is less effective. ResNet50 shows the opposite behavior: mixed training remains strong across both robustness dimensions, which suggests better

Fig. 7. Epoch-wise training dynamics: top row shows aggregate score trajectories for each architecture; lower rows show clean, PGD, and IBAE metric trajectories by architecture and regime.

objective integration. EfficientNet-B0 sits between these two cases and shows partial integration: mixed training helps, but regime-specific preferences remain visible.

This interpretation supports a practical guideline: regime choice should be architecture-aware. For smaller backbones, specialization by threat type may be the safer strategy. For larger backbones, mixed training can better exploit shared structure between perturbation robustness and invariance robustness. More broadly, reporting only one architecture can hide important robustness behavior and may lead to overgen-

eralized conclusions.

C. Cross-Source IBAE Transfer Implications

The additional ResNet mixed transfer experiment sharpens the interpretation of invariance-based training data as a model-dependent signal rather than a fully interchangeable robustness resource. Cross-source mixed training (using EfficientNet- or MobileNet-generated IBAE) preserved clean accuracy but reduced robustness terms compared with in-domain ResNet-source training. This suggests that while the mixed objective remains beneficial in principle, the quality of the IBAE su-

Fig. 8. Top-1 checkpoint score under alternative weighting policies.

pervision depends on the source model that produced those examples.

The empirical observation is therefore straightforward: with all other settings fixed, cross-source IBAE training reduced score relative to in-domain IBAE training while leaving clean accuracy nearly unchanged. A plausible mechanism is representation mismatch: IBAE produced from a different backbone may encode invariance patterns aligned with that source model’s decision structure, but only partially aligned with the target ResNet features. Under this hypothesis, cross-source IBAE still provide useful robustness pressure, but with weaker coupling to the target model’s failure modes than in-domain IBAE. The observed increase in invariance failure rates under cross-source training is consistent with this hypothesis, but does not by itself prove mechanism.

Practically, this implies that robustness pipelines should treat IBAE provenance as an experimental factor. If compute budget allows, source-matched IBAE generation appears preferable for maximizing final robustness. When source-matched generation is not feasible, cross-source IBAE may still be useful, but should be expected to incur a measurable robustness gap and therefore should be validated explicitly in checkpoint selection.

D. Limitations

Several limitations should be considered when interpreting the reported results. First, the experiments are conducted on Imagenette, a 10-class subset of ImageNet with comparatively clear class semantics. While this choice enables controlled and reproducible adversarial fine-tuning experiments, it limits direct external validity to more complex datasets and real-world deployment conditions. Robustness behavior observed here may change under higher class counts, finer-grained visual categories, or stronger domain shift.

Second, attack and robustness evaluation are restricted to a specific threat setup. Sensitivity-based robustness is measured primarily via the configured PGD setting, while invariance-based robustness depends on the employed IBAE generation pipeline (including pairing strategy, explainability method, and construction hyperparameters). Different attack strengths, additional attack families, or alternative IBAE construction methods could alter both absolute performance and relative

ranking. Therefore, the current results should be interpreted as robust within the defined protocol, not as a complete characterization of worst-case robustness.

Third, the aggregate score used for ranking introduces an explicit normative choice through fixed weights ($0.4 A_{\text{clean}}(m) + 0.3 A_{\text{PGD}}(m) + 0.3 A_{\text{IBAE}}(m)$). This is appropriate for the objective defined in this work, but it is not unique. Different application priorities could justify different weightings, which may change the preferred checkpoint. To address this, we additionally report disaggregated metrics and score decomposition, yet any single scalar ranking remains policy-dependent.

Finally, compute-budget and experimental-scope constraints limit exploration depth. The study focuses on three CNN families and fixed fine-tuning schedules; broader architecture coverage, longer schedules, and expanded hyperparameter sweeps may reveal additional interactions between capacity, regime choice, and robustness outcomes. These limitations do not invalidate the main findings, but they bound their generality and motivate the future-work directions.

E. Practical Implications and Model Selection Guidance

From a deployment perspective, the results suggest a two-step decision process. First, choose the architecture class according to resource budget and required robustness profile. In this study, ResNet50 provides the strongest overall robustness–accuracy balance, EfficientNet-B0 offers a competitive middle ground, and MobileNetV3 can remain attractive when efficiency constraints dominate and specialization by threat type is acceptable.

Second, choose the training regime based on threat priority. If balanced robustness against both perturbation-oriented and invariance-oriented attacks is required, mixed training is the most reliable choice for higher-capacity backbones. If one threat class dominates the risk model, specialized regimes can be preferable (e.g., SBAE-only for stronger PGD robustness, IBAE-only for lower invariance failure with minimal clean-accuracy regression).

At the same time, model selection should not rely on a single scalar score without context. The aggregate score is useful for consistent checkpoint tracking, but deployment decisions should additionally consider disaggregated metrics, especially invariance failure and clean-accuracy tolerance. In practice, the recommended procedure is therefore: define threat priorities, define acceptable clean-performance loss, and then select architecture and regime jointly under those constraints.

VII. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

A. Summary of Findings

This work investigated how sensitivity-based and invariance-based adversarial examples can be integrated into a practical fine-tuning pipeline for image classifiers on Imagenette. Across MobileNetV3, ResNet50, and EfficientNet-B0, baseline checkpoints consistently achieved high clean accuracy but weak adversarial robustness, confirming that clean performance alone is not a sufficient proxy for robust behavior.

Fig. 9. Cross-source transfer in ResNet mixed training. Left: aggregate score $S(m)$ as defined in Section III-E. Right: IBAE target-label accuracy only. In-domain ResNet-source IBAE training remains strongest; cross-source variants preserve clean behavior but reduce robustness terms.

The empirical results showed a clear regime effect. SBAE-only training provided the strongest gains in PGD robustness, while IBAE-only training provided the strongest gains on invariance-oriented robustness metrics and was often the most clean-preserving regime. Mixed training yielded the best overall balance in higher-capacity backbones, but was less effective for smaller models where objective interference appeared stronger. This demonstrated that robustness optimization was both threat-dependent and architecture-dependent.

At the architecture level, ResNet50 established the strongest robustness–accuracy frontier under the selected score definition, with the mixed checkpoint reaching the top aggregate performance. EfficientNet-B0 formed an intermediate tier, while MobileNetV3 benefited more from specialized regimes than from mixed optimization. This main result stayed the same in an additional sensitivity check with geometric and quadratic score aggregation. These alternative formulations changed some ordering among specialized checkpoints (SBAE-only tended to rank somewhat higher and IBAE-only somewhat lower), but they did not change the top architecture-level conclusion. The cross-architecture ranking and score decomposition jointly showed that top checkpoints were selected primarily through robustness composition rather than differences in clean accuracy, which were comparatively small.

A further contribution of this work is methodological: checkpoint selection was integrated into an automatic score-based tracking rule across epochs, and results were reported in both aggregated and disaggregated form. This supports reproducible, policy-aware model selection rather than ad-hoc manual checkpoint picking. Overall, practical robustness tuning should be treated as a multi-objective design problem where architecture choice, regime choice, and deployment priorities are aligned explicitly.

B. Future Work

Several directions can extend and strengthen the findings of this work. First, robustness evaluation should be broadened beyond the current threat setup. On the sensitivity side, this includes stronger and more diverse attacks (e.g., different PGD budgets, AutoAttack-style suites, transfer-based attacks).

On the invariance side, future work should compare alternative IBAE generation strategies, evaluate semantic consistency more directly, and test robustness under compression or transformation pipelines.

Second, external validity should be improved by moving from Imagenette to larger and more complex datasets, as well as out-of-distribution scenarios. This would clarify whether the observed architecture–regime interaction (specialization in smaller backbones vs. balanced mixed gains in larger backbones) generalizes beyond the current benchmark.

Third, the model-selection policy itself should be stress-tested. Since checkpoint ranking depends on score weights, future work should run explicit weight-sensitivity analyses and potentially learn deployment-specific utility functions instead of fixing one static weighting. This can make selection more transparent for domain-specific risk profiles.

Finally, the pipeline can be expanded toward practical deployment constraints: compute-efficient robustness tuning, calibration and uncertainty estimation under attack, and monitoring for robustness drift after deployment. Together, these extensions would make the framework even more applicable to real deployment settings.

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